

Deliverable D17.2

The AAI for TREs Blueprint, second version

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Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Contribution towards project objectives	5
Objective 1	5
Objective 2	5
Objective 3	6
Objective 4	6
3. Definitions / Glossary	7
4. Introduction / Background	9
5. Requirements for AAAI	11
5.1 Overview of the requirements	12
5.1.1 Functional requirements	13
5.1.2 Non-Functional requirements	19
6. Blueprint Architecture	20
6.1. Authentication	21
6.2. Authorisation and Access Control	22
6.2.1. The relation of the ABAC model and GA4GH Passport	24
6.2.2. ABAC in EOSC-ENTRUST Federation of TREs	24
6.2.3. Authorisation Use Cases	26
6.3. Accounting and Auditing	26
7. Revisions since AARC-BPA-2019-Final	28
8. Conclusions	28
9. Next Steps	29
10. Impact	31
11. References	31

1. Executive Summary

The mission of EOSC-ENTRUST is to create a European network of trusted research environments (TREs) for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability through the joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. This document presents the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) Blueprint for TREs, a critical component designed to complement the broader TRE architecture by addressing the unique challenges of managing sensitive data, especially controlling access to them.

Recognizing that the current landscape of TREs is fragmented—with researchers encountering a multitude of disparate systems and providers struggling with incompatible technology and governance frameworks—the AAAI Blueprint builds upon the established AARC Blueprint Architecture and its guidelines. However, the demanding requirements of TREs necessitate targeted enhancements. Specifically, the Blueprint extends the traditional framework through four key improvements:

1. **Account Creation:** Secure and efficient processes for provisioning user identities that are tailored to the operational context of TREs.
2. **Identity Vetting:** Rigorous verification methods that ensure users are who they claim to be, thereby facilitating reliable access across national borders.
3. **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC):** A fine-grained authorisation model that evaluates not only the conventional subject, object, and operation but also the surrounding environment, thereby centralizing and standardizing policy decisions.
4. **Accounting Layer:** An advanced framework for monitoring, auditing, and tracking usage, which is essential for identifying and responding to potential violations or unauthorized access.

These enhancements are the direct result of a detailed analysis of TRE requirements, addressing heightened security needs, improved interoperability, and stringent accountability. The outcome is a comprehensive set of requirements and recommendations that AAAI implementations within the EOSC-ENTRUST federation are expected to follow, ensuring that the security infrastructure is both robust and adaptable to the evolving landscape of sensitive data management.

Compared with the first version, this second version clarifies that the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI is not a single AAAI instance to be implemented, but a federation framework combining centralised AAAI components with AA(A)I capabilities at the level of individual TREs. It also refines the requirements based on feedback from the project drivers, including requirements identified in D7.1 and MS8, and strengthens the baseline by adding a security requirement based on the AARC Security Operational Baseline. The Blueprint further clarifies the role of identity wallets in relation to eIDASv2: they are recognised as an

important future capability, but remain a SHOULD requirement at this stage because the wider wallet ecosystem is not yet mature enough to make them mandatory.

This Blueprint should be read as a reference architecture and conformance baseline. The normative elements are expressed through the requirement levels in Chapter 5 and through explicitly referenced AARC guidelines. Implementation details, such as software choices, event formats, deployment patterns, and detailed operational procedures, are intentionally left outside the Blueprint and are addressed in complementary guidance documents, including the Accounting/Auditing Design Document and the Accounting/Auditing Service User Guide.

The core architecture remains largely stable in this version, because several relevant external developments are still ongoing, including the evolution of the EOSC Federation architecture, the renewal of the AARC Blueprint Architecture, and the finalisation and adoption of OpenID Federation. The final year-three version will use experience from demonstrators, implementation work, and these external developments to further refine or rebase the Blueprint where appropriate.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise, select 'No'.]

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	Yes

	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 3	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

contributions to selected transnational programmes

Objective 4

The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.

1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).

No

2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).

No

3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).

No

4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)

No

3. Definitions / Glossary

See [1] for the EOSC-ENTRUST glossary.

AAAI

Authentication, Authorization, Auditing/Account Infrastructure

AARC

Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration. The H2020 project (with a follow-up of AARC2 and the currently running AARC TREE) played a key role in developing a reference blueprint - known as the AARC Blueprint Architecture - that guides secure authentication and authorization practices within research infrastructures and EOSC.

ABAC

Attribute-Based Access Control

Accounting

The act of collecting information on resource usage for the purpose of trend analysis, auditing, billing, or cost allocation. [6]

AEGIS

AARC Engagement Group for Infrastructures

Auditing

The act of reviewing accounting records, procedures, and activities to ensure compliance with established policies, standards, and regulations.

Bona-Fide Researcher, Bona-Fide Rights

A user that has been verified as a researcher in the scientific community [7]

BPA

Blueprint architecture

Data Applicant

An organization, institution, or individual that formally requests access to data housed within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE)

Data Consumer

Academic researchers or commercial researchers [2]

Data Controller

According to Article 4(7) of the GDPR, a Data Controller is defined as “the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.”

In a less formal way, the data controller is usually a person or an institution responsible for deciding why and how personal data is processed, and for ensuring that the processing complies with the GDPR's requirements.

Data Custodian

Defined in [2] as responsible for curating and maintaining complete, accurate and useful sets of public data (a technical branch of data controllership, perhaps)

Data Provider

An organisation, institution, or individual that provides the data to a TRE, this may include public health registries [3]; members of the public, data controllers, and data custodians [2]

Data Repository

An institution that stores the data

Data Sharing Agreement

Agreement between a Data Controller and a Data Repository, outlines the terms and conditions for sharing data, including licensing, access controls, and data use limitations

Data Transfer Agreement

An agreement between the Data Controller and Data Applicant when data is physically transferred to the applicant. This type of agreement outlines the responsibilities and security measures required for handling the transferred data.

Data Use Agreement

An agreement between the Data Controller and Data Applicant when the applicant accesses and uses data on its original premises, such as within a TRE maintained by the data holder. This ensures that data remains under the custodianship of the provider while the applicant is granted controlled access.

eID

Electronic identification scheme following the eIDAS Regulation [8]

eIDAS

Electronic IDentification, Authentication, and Trust Services, EU Regulations [8] [9]

EDIF

European Digital Identity Framework [9]

EKYC

Electronic Know Your Customer, automated process through which entities can perform customer identity verification digitally

FURMS

Fenix User and Resource Management Service

GA4GH

Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

GDI

Genomic Data Infrastructure

GDPR

General Data Protection Regulation

IdP

Identity Provider

MFA

Multi-factor authentication

OPA

Open Policy Agent

PEP

Policy Enforcement Point

PDP

Policy Decision Point

PIP

Policy Information Point

PAP

Policy Administration Point

RBAC

Role-Based Access Control

REMS

Resource Entitlement Management System

SGAS

Swedish Grid Accounting System

SIEM

Security information and event management

SP

Service Provider

SPE

Secure Processing Environment

TRE

Trusted Research Environment

4. Introduction / Background

The mission of EOSC-ENTRUST project is to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.

Today, while a significant number of TREs are in operation, the landscape remains fragmented. Researchers encounter a variety of disparate systems and access procedures, and providers face the challenge of managing federated access across multiple, often incompatible, technology and governance frameworks. This fragmentation underscores the need for a unified approach that not only standardizes access protocols but also accommodates the stringent security and operational requirements associated with sensitive data.

EOSC-ENTRUST brings together providers and developers of operational Trusted Research Environments from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational, and technical language.

The AAAI Blueprint for TREs aims to provide an integrated architecture for the authentication, authorisation, accounting, and auditing of TREs. It builds on the established AARC Blueprint Architecture (AARC BPA) [4] and the related guidelines [5] as a mandatory starting point for developing the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI. However, TREs dealing with sensitive data introduce additional challenges that require tailored enhancements beyond the conventional AARC approach.

In this context, deliverable D17.2 focuses on the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) as a crucial, complementary component of the overall TRE architecture outlined in D13.4 [25] and D14.3 [26]. The EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI is not a specific AAAI instance to be implemented, but a framework that encompasses both centralized AAAI components complemented by specific AA(A)I at the individual TREs

level. This Blueprint describes requirements this AAAI federation has to follow to guarantee a full interoperability to create a unified AAAI user experience.

This Blueprint is intended to be used as a reference architecture and conformance baseline for the EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI federation. Normative expectations are expressed through the requirement levels in Chapter 5, using the RFC 2119 terminology, and through explicitly referenced AARC BPA guidelines where compliance is stated as required. Implementations joining the federation are expected to satisfy the MUST requirements and to align with SHOULD requirements unless a justified alternative is documented. The architecture diagrams and explanatory text provide guidance on the functional decomposition, interoperability model, and expected information flows, but they do not prescribe specific software products, deployment models, or detailed policy texts. Such implementation-level guidance may be provided in complementary documents, such as the Accounting/Auditing Design Document and the Accounting/Auditing Service User Guide; these documents support implementation and piloting, but are not themselves normative parts of this Blueprint.

Taking into account the unique requirements imposed by the sensitive nature of the data, the AAAI Blueprint for TREs extends the AARC Blueprint by incorporating the following four key enhancements:

1) Account Creation

Establishes secure, streamlined procedures for provisioning user accounts tailored to the operational context of TREs.

2) Identity Vetting

Implements rigorous identity verification processes to ensure that only duly authenticated users are granted access, thereby reinforcing trust in the system.

3) Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC)

Adopts advanced access control mechanisms that evaluate user attributes and contextual factors, enabling fine-grained permission management.

4) Accounting Layer

Develops an enhanced framework for monitoring, recording, and auditing access activities, ensuring transparency and compliance with security requirements.

By integrating these enhancements, the EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI Blueprint not only adheres to the mandatory foundation provided by the AARC Blueprint Architecture but also evolves it to meet the specific demands of TREs. The introduction of secure account creation establishes a robust process for provisioning user identities, ensuring consistency and security from the outset. Strengthened identity vetting is designed to verify that users are who they claim to be, thereby facilitating reliable access across national borders and diverse governance frameworks.

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) is employed to enable fine-grained contextualized authorisation decisions. By considering not only the traditional factors—such as the subject, object, and operation—but also the broader environmental context (e.g. time of day, geographic location), ABAC supports centralized management of authorisation policies. This approach relieves individual services from implementing their own decision mechanisms and guarantees uniformity in policy enforcement across the federation.

The addition of an advanced accounting layer serves a dual purpose. It provides continuous monitoring for any potential violations or unauthorized access while also maintaining comprehensive audit trails for tracking incidents when they occur. Moreover, by offering federated points for critical components like identity vetting and authorisation policy management, the Blueprint implementation will improve interoperability. This ensures that all services within the federation can rely on consistent AAA-related functionality and decision-making made by the centralised AAAI, ultimately reinforcing the overall security and operational integrity of TREs. Services do not need to implement such components themselves and they can trust that the AAA-related (or at least the Authentication and Authorization-related) functionality and decisions, directly related to the authentication and authorisation layer (plus audit data from the accounting), are the same across the whole federation.

This AAAI Blueprint represents the year-two version of our effort, establishing a solid foundation based on the AARC Blueprint while addressing the unique challenges of TREs. The AAAI Blueprint for TREs will undergo regular revisions and refinement, with a yearly publication. Some areas of interest have already been identified, and these are discussed in detail in Chapter 9, Next steps.

5. Requirements for AAAI

In this chapter, we define the requirements of EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI and describe the vital features and standards for secure and user-friendly access within the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. We start by stating that the AAAI MUST implement the AARC Blueprint Architecture and the related guidelines and then extend that baseline with further requirements. The requirements were collected by the members from other work packages in the EOSC-ENTRUST project as well as other sources the project members were familiar with. These requirements establish a framework to ensure reliable security, compliance, and efficient user interactions by covering functional needs like identity assurance and access control and non-functional needs like scalability and privacy. Some of the collected requirements overlapped, so a curated list of final requirements is found in Tables 1 and 2 in this document. Table 1 collects functional requirements and Table 2 non-functional ones.

5.1 Overview of the requirements

Below is an overview of the curated requirements. The requirements are assigned an identifier (R1, R2, ...Rn) for unambiguous referencing. The key words “MUST”, “MUST NOT”, “REQUIRED”, “SHALL”, “SHALL NOT”, “SHOULD”, “SHOULD NOT”, “RECOMMENDED”, “MAY”, and “OPTIONAL” in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC2119 [24].

We identified five groups within the requirements: user identity, access control, accounting and auditing, infrastructure, and agreements and entitlements. The groups roughly line up with the layers represented by different colours in the Blueprint in chapter 6. The same colour schema is followed in Table 1. The requirements have been colour coded to match layers in the Blueprint where applicable (see Fig. 1). Requirements without colour coding (esp. the whole Table 2) apply across multiple layers or to the AAI as a whole. In this chapter, we first give an overview of how the requirements fit into these groups and then expand on each requirement in chapters 5.1.1 and 5.1.2.

User identity related requirements

Requirements R9, R13, R14, R15, R21, R22 and R36 concern user identity, where user refers to a natural person accessing the ENTRUST federation and performing authentication and authorisation through the AAI. They define how user accounts are created and linked together as well as how user identities are verified (identity vetting). They concern User Identity and Community Attribute Services layers in the Blueprint.

Access control related requirements

One of the primary functions of the AAI is access control and authorisation. Requirements R9, R14, R17, R18, R20 as well as R11 and R12 concern access control and authorisation with R17 being the most important one and the others complementing it.

Accounting and Auditing related requirements

The requirements R2, R3, R4, R6, R7 and R8 form the basis of accounting and auditing in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Together they form the Accounting layer in the Blueprint.

Infrastructure related requirements

Requirements R23, R24, R27 and R33 deal with Access Protocol Translation layer in the Blueprint. They define how home organisations and services can integrate with the AAI and what kind of access protocols should be used.

Agreements and entitlements related requirements

Accepting agreements and policies (such as acceptable use policy) and completing trainings (i.e., who did completed which training, who and when accepted access

conditions) were identified as requirements for the AAAI. These are handled in Requirements R11 and R12.

The AAAI itself has regulations and policies it must follow. These are discussed in requirements R3 and R16.

5.1.1 Functional requirements

ID	Name	Requirement Level	Description
R2	Technology-Agnostic Accounting Data Collection	MUST	The AAAI must ensure accounting data collection is independent of specific technologies (e.g., Perun, SATOSA, SimpleSAMLphp, Keycloak). API-based data collection will enable seamless interoperability, allowing data to be aggregated, analysed, and reported in a unified manner regardless of the underlying AAAI technology
R4	Data Analytics and Reporting	SHOULD	The AAAI should provide analytics tools for monitoring accounting data, detecting patterns, risks, or misconfigurations in real-time
R6	Access Control for Accounting Data	MUST	The AAAI must support roles and access levels for who can view or modify accounting data, ensuring only authorised personnel or services can access sensitive logs
R7	Notifications and Alerts	SHOULD	The AAAI should support real-time alerts when suspicious activities or anomalies are detected (e.g., failed authentications, access policy violations)
R8	Trace/Audit log	MUST	The AAAI must collect/log detailed information on all authentication and authorisation events, including user identifiers, timestamps, IP addresses, authentication methods, and authorisation decisions. These logs must retain system-generated information that allows the reconstruction of a coherent and complete view of activity (the 'who, what, where, when, why', and 'to whom') for auditing and security incident investigation purposes

R9	MFA	MUST	AAAI must be able to perform MFA when required
R11	Agreements	MUST	AAAI must indicate which agreements the user has accepted
R12	Entitlements	MUST	AAAI must indicate which training the user has passed and use this data for authorisation decisions.
R13	Account Creation	MUST	The AAAI must provide a solution that enables new users to create an account within the EOSC-ENTRUST federation
R14	Identity Assurance	MUST	AAAI must provide a mechanism to verify the authenticity and legitimacy of an individual's identity. This should include users outside of the EU.
R15	Identity Freshness	MUST	AAAI must verify that the users' digital identity is still valid
R16	Anonymisation	SHOULD	AAAI should provide a solution for anonymising users' data where that data is directly managed by the AAAI and to be used outside AAAI
R17	Access Control	MUST	AAAI must offer a way to manage entitlements and permissions of a user to access digital resources such as datasets or computing services. These permissions and entitlements must be stored and communicated according to community standards implemented in science and e-Infrastructure clusters in Europe. Managing predefined authorisation rules must be included. This includes but is not limited to

			<p>Bona-Fide rights for access and group membership-based access. Furthermore, users must be able to select which attributes, groups or roles are used for a particular authorisation decision.</p> <p>This requirement deals with user data included within the AAI, not the data it helps to control access to.</p>
R18	Authorisation Delegation	MUST	AAAI must provide a service to TREs for enforcing data permissions, grants, and entitlements of users and projects.
R19	Access Request	MUST	AAAI must provide a solution which allows users/projects to request access to resources and services within a specific TRE
R20	Access Suspension and revocation	MUST	AAAI must provide a solution to deny individual users (or entire IdPs) access to TREs in case of a security incident
R21	AAAI-hosted IdP	MUST	AAAI must provide a way to manage accounts for users without a home organisation account
R22	Account Linking	SHOULD	AAAI should provide a way to link users' different digital identities into a single account. Linking ORCID specifically is likely to be needed. See also R26 that introduces a unique identifier.
R23	Definition of protocols	MUST	AAAI must provide and document a set of protocols that must be supported by individual SPs/TREs/IdPs in order to integrate with the EOSC-ENTRUST federation

R24	Registering SPs and IdPs	MUST	AAAI must provide a solution for integrating new SPs and IdPs.
R27	Smart Discovery	SHOULD	The IdP discovery should be “smart enough” to quickly and easily take a user to their appropriate home IdP.
R33	Non-web use cases	MUST	The AAAI system must enable authentication and authorisation via non-web use cases, as many interactions between clients and servers are via the user’s command line or via interacting applications using APIs.
R35	AARC BPA Compliance	MUST	The AAAI system must comply with the AARC Blueprint Architecture [4], which serves as the baseline architecture for the EOSC AAI (EOSC AAI Architecture 2022 [11]), and adhere to the related interoperability guidelines [5] endorsed by AEGIS [12].
R36	Identity Wallets	SHOULD ²	The AAAI system should integrate wallet-based authentication to align with eIDASv2 regulations. This integration should support the EU Digital Wallet and national wallets, ensuring compliance with eIDASv2 standards.

Table 1: Functional requirements

The requirements have been color coded to match layers in the Blueprint (see Fig 1) where applicable. Requirements without colour coding apply across multiple layers or to the AAAI as a whole.

Requirement R2 Technology-Agnostic Accounting Data Collection normalises the collected data to be independent of AAAI systems by using an API-based data collection model. This enables both internal AAAI services (e.g. Community Attribute Services, Proxy, etc.) and external consumer services to send accounting information to the accounting service regardless of their infrastructure or technology stacks.

² The Identity wallets are expected to become mandatory in some future version of this Blueprint, but at this moment the whole eWallet ecosystem (and also the general AAI Blueprint) are not mature enough to make them a mandatory requirement.

Centralized accounting data only achieves its full potential when paired with robust analysis capabilities. Requirement R4 mandates that the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI SHOULD incorporate analytical tools designed to identify risks, intrusions, and other anomalies in normal operations, and to further enhance threat detection and response, the accounting service SHOULD integrate with SIEM tools.

Requirement R6 mandates having access controls for accounting data. The accounting service MUST support roles and access levels, so each user can have a completely different access rights to the accounting data. Access MUST be granted only to authorised personnel and any changes to existing accounting data MUST leave an audit trail.

Requirement R7 covers real-time notifications and alerts based on accounting data. These can be valuable in detecting risks and issues, but care must be taken to define conditions to maintain a good signal-to-noise ratio and to prevent false alerts.

Requirement R8 mandates minimal requirements for what accounting data MUST be collected. In short, the collected data must be sufficient to answer the questions of who, what, where, when, why and to whom about any activity or decision taking place in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Care must be taken to minimise the amount of personally identifiable information included in accounting data and to comply with any relevant privacy regulations. Opaque identifiers should be used whenever possible.

Requirement R9 mandates performing multi-factor authentication (MFA) when required by the service. This is covered by BPA Guideline AARC-G029. We extend this by making the ability to perform MFA a MUST requirement rather than SHOULD. It is important to note that MFA should only be performed once per login for usability reasons, so if the user's home organisation already performs MFA then the AAAI should accept that and not require a second MFA.

Users may be required to review and accept various agreements and policies before accessing services in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Requirement R11 specifies that the AAAI MUST collect and maintain a list of agreements the user has accepted and use that to support authorisation decisions. These MUST be expressed using entitlements similar to how group memberships are expressed in AARC-G069 and resource capabilities are expressed in AARC-G027.

Many external consumer services may require service-specific training before allowing users access to the service. Similarly, an EOSC-ENTRUST federation-wide initial training may be required of all users. Requirement R12 mandates that the AAAI MUST collect and maintain information on what training the user has completed and use that information to support authorisation decisions. These MUST be expressed using entitlements similar to

how group memberships are expressed in AARC-G069 and resource capabilities are expressed in AARC-G027.

Requirement R14 mandates a mechanism to perform identity vetting as a MUST. This means the AAAI MUST have a way to tie a user account to a natural person with a high level of assurance. The EOSC-ENTRUST federation will handle sensitive data, so the ability to ensure who is behind a user account is important. This requirement forms the Identity vetting component in the Blueprint. Identity vetting is split between Community Attribute Services and User Identity layers because it can be performed by either a service belonging to the AAAI or an external service.

Requirement R15 mandates ensuring identity freshness. This means making sure that user attributes such as affiliations are up to date. Usually, this is implemented by requiring users to refresh the attributes (e.g. by performing federated login again) after a given time frame. A common time frame is once a year (every 12 months).

Requirement R16 concerns anonymising user data. Requirement R3 is also related to this. The AAAI MUST define and document policies and procedures for compliance with regulations and anonymising user data. It may not be possible to anonymise accounting data, but using opaque identifiers should help maximise user data privacy in accounting data.

Requirement R17 deals with access control. This is a complex topic with numerous details. The main requirement is that AAAI MUST be able to make authorisation decisions at the Proxy (see Fig. 1) based on predefined access rules. It MUST be possible to define both global rules (that affect all end services) as well as end service-specific rules. This is also covered by BPA Guideline AARC-I047, but we extend it to MUST rather than SHOULD. R17 mandates that at a minimum access rules MUST include the ability to require Bona Fide status from a user or group membership. Other requirements extend this minimum requirement. Requirement R9 mandates that the AAAI MUST be able to require MFA for access. Requirement R14 mandates that AAAI MUST be able to require successful identity vetting for access. Requirements R11 and R12 specify that the AAAI MUST be able to require accepted agreements or passed training courses for access. Finally, R17 mandates that users MUST be able to select which of their attributes (kept by AAAI) are used for a particular access request. This enables using the least amount of privileges required for a task, e.g. a project manager may login as a project member if they do not need manager-level access. Using only required attributes supports user privacy and data minimisation as well.

Requirement R18 mandates that the AAAI MUST provide a way for end services to define access rules mentioned in R17.

Requirement R21 mandates that the AAAI **MUST** provide a way to manage accounts for users without a home organisation account. This is needed for users coming from smaller public or not-for-profit as well as commercial organisations, as they may not have an account from a federated home organization.

Requirement R22 specifies that the AAAI **SHOULD** allow users to link multiple external identities into a single identity in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. This should be implemented according to BPA Guideline AARC-G009. Requirements R13 and R21 are related to this as well and should be taken into consideration when implementing R22.

Requirement R24 mandates a centralised resource register solution for integrating new SPs, IdPs and Attribute Authorities as community attribute services to the AAAI federation.

The expectation of Requirement 27 is that a smart IdP discovery service **SHOULD** be available to select home IdP based on short lists. Shortlists can be tailored by country, institute, e-infrastructure, research community, project or other clues. This discovery service requirement is covered in guidelines AARC-G061, AARC-G062 and AARC-G063.

Requirement R33 specifies that the AAAI **MUST** enable access to end services via non-web use cases. This is covered by AARC BPA Guidelines AARC-G004, AARC-G005, AARC-G007 and AARC-G010.

Requirement R36 is a speculative one at this point. Requirement R14 mandates identity vetting, and the most reliable way to do this would be with government-backed electronic identification (eID) as specified by the eIDASv1 regulation [8]. However, this method is not usable for everyone in the EU due to differences in national implementations of eIDASv1. The updated regulation eIDASv2 [9] should ease the use of eIDs by way of digital wallets and enable far wider usage than eIDASv1 did. Wallets and eIDASv2 are not yet usable or available, so R36 specifies that they should be used once they become available.

The not explicitly commented requirement (R13, R19, R20, R23, R35) are considered self-explanatory in the tables.

5.1.2 Non-Functional requirements

ID	Name	Requirement Level	Description
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R3	Compliance and Privacy	MUST	The AAAI must comply with privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR) and implement best practices to minimise data exposure. This includes documented data anonymisation, retention policies, and secure storage.
R5	Performance and Scalability	MUST	The AAAI must be able to accommodate a high number of users, services, and communities and must be able to scale as these numbers grow. The AAAI must set performance benchmarks and scalability requirements to handle expected loads (e.g., user authentications, AAAI API calls).
R10	Usability	SHOULD	User experience and ease of use should be evaluated and taken into account when implementing the AAAI for TREs. This is especially important due to the high security requirements for all TREs components, where such security requirements can lead to a cumbersome user experience for end users.
R25	Unique identifier for projects	MUST	The project identifier must be globally recognisable and unique within the Federation.
R26	Unique identifier for users	MUST	The user identifier must be globally recognisable and unique within the Federation.
R37	Security	MUST	The AAAI must implement AARC-G084 [27] Security Operational Baseline at a minimum.

Table 2: Non-functional requirements

Requirement R3 mandates that the AAAI MUST comply with various regulations and policies. A complete list of regulations and policies is outside the scope of this document, but AARC BPA Guidelines AARC-G014, AARC-G015, AARC-G016, AARC-G042, and AARC-G071 offer recommendations and templates for various documents the AAAI must provide.

Requirements R25 and R26 mandate that the AAAI MUST provide globally unique identifiers for projects and users, respectively. These both should be issued following AARC

BPA Guidelines AARC-G026 and AARC-G031. The identifiers for users should be globally unique, persistent, permanent, and opaque. The identifiers for projects should be globally unique, persistent, and permanent.

As above, the not-commented requirements (R5, R10, R37) are considered self-explanatory.

5.3 Validating AAI requirements against drivers' requirements

Drivers have performed analysis and review of their requirements during the second year of the project, most notably in deliverable D7.1 "Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis" [35] and MS8 [36]. Both mention requirements relevant to our collected requirements, and to the AAI Blueprint. Here we review those requirements to make sure our collected AAI requirements and our Blueprint covers them.

Drivers identified five new requirements related to AAI in D7.1 [35]. These are collected in Table 3.

ID	Description	Covered by
D7.1-01	Central registration system in a unified service portal: this should allow users to register at a central point in the federation as a means to register to all TREs within it. The central registration is not a property of AAI, but should be linked to the AAI service in order to keep track of users' authorisations within the federation.	R13
D7.1-02	Should allow for authentication of non-European users who do not have access to eID or nationals from EU countries where national regulations do not support eID or where there are restrictions on which countries within EU are trusted.	R14
D7.1-03	User training and certification should be included in AAI ("Researcher passport").	R12
D7.1-04	There could be specific criteria for the authentication methods, such as biometrics etc.	R9
D7.1-05	Entitlements based on contracts between TREs and commercial parties (Driver 4).	R35

Table 3: AAI related requirements from D7.1 [35]

Requirements D7.1-01 and D7.1-03 - D7.1-05 are already covered by our existing requirements and Blueprint. D7.1-01 is covered by R13, D7.1-03 is covered by R12, D7.1-04 is covered by requirements R9 and the ability for TREs to request specific authentication methods, which is standard functionality for AAI systems stemming from e.g. AARC Guideline AARC-G029 [37].

Requirement D7.1-02 is more complex. Currently this Blueprint simply states "AAAI must provide a mechanism to verify the authenticity and legitimacy of an individual's identity" in R14. R14 covers D7.1-02 in principle, but without considering specific means to do so. Projects like GDI and FEGA are considering eWallets to solve similar requirements, but this is still an emerging technology and it will take some time to take it into use. Similar issues have been recognised in Finland in the context of foreigners arriving to Finland to work or to study. Under Finnish legislation individuals need to be identified (identity vetted) before being granted a Finnish social security number, which in turn is a requirement for completing the immigration process (for long term immigration). Currently, the best available solution to these kinds of requirements appear to be various commercial solutions that aim to identify users based on biological data in passports or governmental IDs and matching those to the user with a smartphone app. While we can not offer or commit to any particular solution to this requirement, we note that D7.1-02 is included in R14 and we are aware a solution must be implemented when implementing the ENTRUST Federation. R14 has been modified to specifically include this use case as well.

Driver milestone report MS8 [36] has identified nine requirements relevant to our Blueprint. MS8 also identified three more requirements assigned to AAI, but that are not in scope for the AAI Blueprint. These requirements are collected in Table 4.

ID	Description	Covered by
MS8-R004	Certification and auditing process on the federation level to verify that TREs comply with requirements	Out of scope
MS8-R024	2-factor authentication for TRE users	R9
MS8-R041	Monitoring & Alerting Capabilities: Automated alerts for misuse detection beyond logging/auditing	R7, upgrade to SHOULD
MS8-R045	Central user registration	R31

MS8-R046	Authenticating non-European users who don't have eIDAS and users from member states where national regulations do not support eID (or there are restrictions from which countries within EU are trusted)	R14
MS8-R047	Ability for the AAAI to release trainings user has completed as attributes	R12
MS8-R050	Freshness of identity information of a user logging in to a TRE or the federation should be checked	R15
MS8-R052	AAAI must support authorization based on subject attributes	R17, R18
MS8-R053	Logging and auditing	R2
MS8-R054	Support for querying and filtering audit logs through intuitive user interfaces (dashboards, reports, alerts)	R4
MS8-R062	Automate governance reviews	Out of scope
MS8-R065	GDPR-compliant auditing	Out of scope

Table 4: AAAI related requirements from MS8 [36].

Requirements MS8-R004 and MS8-R065 are out of scope for this Blueprint as AAAI can not handle certifying TREs or other systems as compliant or perform compliance audits. These may be needed in the ENTRUST Federation, but it is not a task for the AAAI which is at its core a technical system rather than a regulation body. Requirement MS8-R062 is likewise out of scope, as it would require similar kind of expertise.

Remaining requirements from MS8 [36] are covered by our existing requirements.

6. Blueprint Architecture

Building on the AARC Blueprint Architecture 2019 [4], we have enhanced the AAI by integrating additional Accounting and Auditing components. For a comprehensive comparison, Chapter 7 ('Revisions') details the differences between the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI for TREs Blueprint and the original AARC Blueprint Architecture, as documented in AARC-BPA-2019-Final.

Figure 1: The AAAI Blueprint³

This diagram illustrates the high-level architecture of the Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) for TREs. The colored background blocks represent key components: secure account creation (processes for registering and managing user accounts), identity vetting (mechanisms to verify that users are who they claim to be), attribute-based access control (fine-grained authorization based on user attributes and contextual factors), and an advanced accounting layer (for collecting, monitoring, and auditing usage data).

The TREs participating in the TRE federation are in the End Services layer. TRE software systems implementing TRE capabilities may integrate with AAAI directly, or via an Infrastructure Proxy ([AARC-G045](#)) if they operate their own AAAI, adding a level of isolation and complexity.

6.1. Authentication

User identity deals with identifying and authenticating users. EOSC-ENTRUST is a closed network, meaning users need an account before being able to become a member and log into a TRE. The *Account Creation* step ensures users have an account that meets the EOSC-ENTRUST requirements or a new one without any access rights is created for them. During this step, the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI assigns a public, permanent, opaque and non-reassignable identifier to the user unique within the TRE federation, and collects user's name, email, organization and affiliations so they (and other information) can be released to

³ Original schema taken from AARC Blueprint Architecture and extended appropriately

TREs following the AARC-G056 guidelines [29]. This implies the TREs must be connected to EOSC-ENTRUST AAI as a Service Provider; we recommend OIDC authorisation code flow [32] with PKCE [33]. The next version of this Blueprint will also cover delegated and “robotic” accesses.

Due to the sensitivity of the data processed in EOSC-ENTRUST, high-quality *Identity Vetting* is a key part of *Account Creation*. User accounts in EOSC-ENTRUST need to be linked to verified identities of natural persons. *Identity Vetting* should be done using an electronic method with sufficient assurance, e.g. eID or an EKYC-process based on government-issued identification documents. EOSC-ENTRUST AAI facilitates the process for better user experience and identity assurances are then released by the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI to the TREs following the AARC-G031 guideline [28]. Note TREs may do their own, additional checks if need be.

Note the guidelines states the identity assurance profiles it defines are only valid for the session, which requires users to log in with specific identity providers. EOSC-ENTRUST should additionally support identity linking and release a custom scoped assurance claim if the user has a medium- or high-assurance identity linked to their AAI account but used a different authentication method for better user experience in cases when this is sufficient to gain access. This is another extension to the AARC BPA that we’re proposing.

Step-Up Authentication should primarily be handled by the user's home organization, ensuring that the initial authentication process is secure. When the home organization does not support MFA, the AAI MUST trigger a backup Step-Up Authentication (the Step up Authn in Fig 1) process to enforce multifactor authentication. Conversely, if MFA has already been successfully completed by the home organization, the AAI SHOULD NOT require users to perform MFA again. Authentication assurances are then released by the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI to the TREs following the REFEDS MFA Profile guideline [34].

The EOSC-ENTRUST AAI session duration should follow the AARC-G081 guideline [31] recommendations. We encourage individual TREs to follow this guideline, too.

6.2. Authorisation and Access Control

Authorisation specifies rights/privileges for accessing resources, more formally defining an access policy enforced by *access control* during usage. This document addresses both federated and non-federated authorisation use cases - *but individual TREs participating in the TRE federation do retain their authority on deciding access* to resources under their control.

There are multiple access control models, the recent ones being Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC). ABAC is more general than RBAC, it

can do everything RBAC can do and more, thus it is recommended by NIST in its publication SP 800-162 [13] for dynamic and complex environments. However, RBAC remains popular as it solves common use cases, and is easier to implement and use. An EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI must be able to support both approaches.

6.2.1. RBAC

RBAC makes access decisions by checking whether a subject (user) has a particular role granting them permission to perform an action with an object (resource). Roles are specific to a system's domain and implementation, but in general, they are better suited to express static policies (as opposed to dynamic conditions) and should be few in number to remain manageable and auditable.

In the context of a TRE federation, RBAC is well-suited to implement access based on the user's TRE federation roles [26] or, for example, having a "certified user" role.

6.2.2. ABAC

ABAC makes access decisions by evaluating rules contained in an access policy against the attributes of:

- *subject* - the user attempting to access a resource
- *object* - the resource being accessed, e.g. a dataset, file, computer, service
- *operation* - the action being attempted e.g. read, delete, view, approve
- *environment* - the context of the access, like time, location or other aspects, e.g. whether it is business hours or a national holiday, whether a state of emergency is declared, whether the price of electric power is high or low, and so on

ABAC recommends the following architecture:

- PEP (Policy Enforcement Point) - enforces policy decisions in response to a request from a subject requesting access to a protected object; the access control decisions are made by the PDP
- PDP (Policy Decision Point) - evaluates incoming requests against policies, returns a Permit/Deny decision
- PIP (Policy Information Point) - the retrieval source of attributes
- PAP (Policy Administration Point) - provides a user interface for creating, managing, testing, and debugging policies, and storing these policies in the appropriate repository

Figure 2: ABAC schema⁴

The diagram above from NIST SP 800-162 shows the components. Decisions are made by Policy Decision Point, which reads policies from Policy Administration Point, reads attributes of subject, object, operation and environment from Policy Information Point, and the decisions are enforced by Policy Enforcement Point.

The components may be centralised or distributed. Typically, the PEP is present at each service, while the PDP may be deployed in multiple instances and located near PEPs for scalability. The important feature is that a policy is shared from a single source and enforced uniformly.

There are two types of access policies:

- digital policy - access control rules that compile directly into machine executable codes or signals
- metapolicy - a policy about policies, or policy for managing policies, such as assignment of priorities and resolution of conflicts between digital policies

An open-source tool for implementation of a PDP is available in Open Policy Agent (OPA, [14]). OPA is a general-purpose policy engine with a high-level declarative language named Rego for specifying policy as code, and simple APIs to offload policy decision-making from software. OPA accepts data about the request and entity attributes in the form of multiple JSON documents. Its output is a single JSON document, containing at least a boolean flag whether access was granted or denied, but can also contain other data. The Rego language

⁴ Figure taken from NIST SP 800-162

provides the syntax for rules transforming input JSON documents into the output JSON document.

The main advantages of specifying a declarative digital access policy as code (compared to hard-coding it in individual software systems) are:

- decouples policy decision-making from policy enforcement
- policy is testable (i.e. it is possible to write unit tests for it)
- policy can be maintained by other administrators than individual software systems, and thus enforced across multiple software systems

In the context of a TRE federation, ABAC is well-suited to enforce TRE federation legal agreements and operating procedures [26] for additional automation of access control.

6.2.3. Authorisation use cases

The federated authorisation use cases which EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI must solve are derived from the Driver user journey [26] and TRE federation operating procedures [26]. Single-TRE authorisation use cases remain sole responsibility of the respective TREs, though they should rely on the EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI which delivers TRE federation level SSO, trusted identity attributes, and federation-wide accounting and audit trail.

Federated analysis is the most interesting use case as it involves most extensively Participants, Actors and policies (as defined in [26]) - and makes most use of EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI. We use this use case to explain the role of AAAI and how it interacts with other parts of the TRE federation. Other use cases (e.g. uploading a sensitive dataset to TRE Secure Data Archive), have analogous solutions.

1. PI registers and authenticates with the TRE Federation using EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI establishing their digital identity and SSO session in the TRE Federation (see 6.1).
2. PI establishes a Project in the Project Registry and creates a Data Access Request in the Discovery Service.
3. Federation Governance distributes PI's Project Application to respective TREs for review by TRE Governance and distributes Data Access Requests to respective TREs for approval by Data Holders (in the simplest federated case, the dataset is in one TRE's Secure Data Holder (SDH) while the research will happen in another TRE's Research Analytics Zone (RAZ)). The resulting agreements (like SLA, DPA, DAA, DUA etc.) are saved in the Agreements Registry.
4. PI invites other Project Members to the Project in the Project Registry. They register and authenticate with the TRE federation (see 6.1), same as the PI in step 1.
5. All Project Members must pass "safe researcher" training, which may happen at the federation level, TRE level, or both. User's certification status is stored in the Users

Registry (conceptually mapping to the User Identity layer combined partially with the Community Attribute Services, being thus part of the EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI).

6. Respective TRE Governance prepares a Project Space in the TRE's RAZ and grants access to the individual Project Members with appropriate roles. Respective Data Holders make the datasets accessible in the Project space.
7. Authorised Project Members analyse the data in the Project Space within the TRE's RAZ. Alternatively, they use Software Service and Job Submission Service to execute a job in the TRE's Query Management Zone (QMZ). Output of the job results post statistical disclosure control is subject to PI approval.
8. PI publishes the results and respective TRE Governance archives the Project Space. The Project is presumably closed in the Project Registry and the Project Members access to resources tied to the Project is revoked across the TRE Federation.

6.2.4. Implementing authorisation in EOOSC-ENTRUST Federation of TREs

The federated analysis use case outlined in the previous section names the most important Actors and Participants engaging in access control as part of each and every action. In this section, we describe how we expect them to make access control decisions.

Note that we assume the Participants are integrated with the EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI for federation-wide Actor identification, SSO, roles, auditing, as well as automation of access control; else, relevant systems interactions must be solved peer-to-peer or done manually.

Similarly, we assume policies and agreements are in a machine-readable format (e.g. JSON with standardised schema) to enable access control automation; else respective processes must be done manually. Note some rules can never be automated (like a promise to cite the datasets used).

Project Registry manages general project information like an identifier, name, start/end date, list of project members and list of authorised datasets. The Registry:

1. Controls access to and management of Project information inside the Registry. RBAC is recommended.
2. Provides project information to other Participants for *their* access control decisions (if it's required). In ABAC terms, it acts as the PIP for Project related environment attributes (e.g. end date), providing these in JSON format. This would be inefficient with RBAC.
 - a. We also expect Project Registry to delegate Project Member management to EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI (either using its API to synchronise the information or just having the PA manage it there), since the AAAI can readily propagate this information to other Participants.

Discovery Service enables searching for datasets within the TRE federation and making Data Access Requests (DAR). The Service:

1. Controls access to and management of DAR information inside the Service. Searches are assumed to be open to the TRE Federation users or public even. RBAC is recommended.
2. Provides DAR information to other Participants for their access control decisions. In ABAC terms, it acts as the PIP for DAR related environment attributes (e.g. date of request), providing these in JSON format.

Federation Participants Registry maintains a list of TREs and other Services forming the TRE Federation and manages their information. The Registry:

1. Controls access to and management of Federation Participant information inside the Registry. RBAC is recommended.
2. Provides Federation Participant information to other Participants for their access control decisions. In ABAC terms, it acts as the PIP for Participant related environment attributes (e.g. country of operation), providing them in JSON format. This would be inefficient with RBAC.

Agreements Registry contains various agreements made by different Actors. The Registry:

1. Controls access to and management of Agreements and their content inside the Registry. RBAC is recommended.
2. Provides the Agreements or their parts to other Participants for their access control decisions. In ABAC terms, it acts as PAP contributing policies to be included and evaluated by relevant PDPs (e.g. enforcement of actionable rules per DUA in RAZ), providing them in JSON format and described in Rego declarative language⁵.

Training Service is currently not described in the EOSC-ENTRUST infrastructure architecture v2 [26], but is implied, as it is required for users to do the actual safe researcher training⁶. The Service:

1. Controls access to and management of training materials inside the Service. RBAC is recommended.
2. Provides user certification information to other Participants for their access control decisions. In ABAC terms, it acts as PIP for training related subject attributes (i.e. “is certified”), providing them in JSON format⁷. Alternatively, Training Service may

⁵ Rego declarative language use is tied to using Open Policy Agent to implement ABAC PDPs. Should a different implementation be used, policy format and language recommendation might change.

⁶ Similar to ELIXIR’s [TeSS](#)

⁷ We do not recommend storing user certification information in EUDIW or its equivalent at this time, since it is a user attribute tied to a specific community (the TRE federation), so we consider the Service or AAAI to be a better fit. Similarly storing the information in a GA4GH visa does not work, since those currently can’t express freshness. We will revisit these points in the final AAAI for TREs Blueprint should there be new developments.

delegate propagation of user certification information to EOSC-ENTRUST AAI (either using its API to synchronise the information or just having the Federation Governance manage it there), since the AAI can readily propagate this information to other Participants. The latter option is better in a mostly RBAC-based federation.

Secure Data Holder (SDH) and Archive (SDA) is a specialized Secure Data Zone (SDZ) for long-term storage of sensitive datasets; one is operated by a Data Controller, the other by a Data Processor with a DPA. The Service:

1. Controls access to and management of the datasets stored inside the Service. There are two ways to implement this:
 - a. RBAC with at least a dataset-level granularity of access control.
 - b. In ABAC terms, the Service acts as PEP and PDP (or is coupled with one). The PDP must obtain and merge all relevant policies from PAP(s) (e.g. DAA) and information from PIP(s) (e.g. Project Registry).

Research Analytics Zone (RAZ) provides a secure environment for interactive analytical work inside of a dedicated Project Space. The Service:

1. Controls access to and management of the Project Spaces inside the Service, and possibly also objects inside of the Project Spaces (e.g. Results). Like with SDZ, there are two ways to implement this:
 - a. RBAC with at least a project-level granularity of access control.
 - b. In ABAC terms, the Service acts as PEP and PDP (or is coupled with one). The PDP must obtain and merge all relevant policies from PAP(s) (e.g. DUA) and information from PIP(s) (e.g. Project Registry).

Job Submission Service manages Job Requests and routes non-interactive analytical Jobs to one or more Query Management Zones. The Service:

1. Controls creation and approval of Job Requests, and submission of Jobs. There are two ways to implement this:
 - a. RBAC with at least a project-level granularity of access control.
 - b. In ABAC terms, the Service acts as PEP and PDP (or is coupled with one). The PDP must obtain and merge all relevant policies from PAP(s) (e.g. a DPA) and information from PIP(s) (e.g. Project Registry).

Query Management Zone (QMZ) executes non-interactive analytical Jobs. The Service:

1. Controls the execution and management of Jobs. There are two ways to implement this:
 - a. RBAC with at least a project-level granularity of access control.
 - b. In ABAC terms, the Service acts as PEP and PDP (or is coupled with one). The PDP must obtain and merge all relevant policies from PAP(s) (e.g. a DUA) and information from PIP(s) (e.g. Project Registry).

General notes on implementation:

In case a Participant uses RBAC, user's roles should come from EOSC-ENTRUST AAI since they are identical across the entire TRE Federation in the federated authorisation use cases. In the simplest case, AAI releases this information during user's authentication to the Participant (see 6.1) in the "entitlements" scope per AARC-G056 [29] and AARC-G069 [30]; though it can also be pre-provisioned, which is useful for offline user access use cases. The Participant then must map this information to its implementation of roles.

Whenever one Participant interacts with another Participant using their respective Security Servers (e.g. a data transfer between TREs), the interaction must be subject to access control and there are two ways to implement it:

1. RBAC with sufficient granularity of access control (e.g. project level).
2. In ABAC terms, the target Participant acts as PEP and PDP (or is coupled with one). The PDP must obtain and merge all relevant policies from PAP(s) (e.g. a DUA) and information from PIP(s) (e.g. Project Registry).

6.3. Accounting and Auditing

Accounting is the process of collecting data to enable *Auditing*. This data must be able to answer the questions of who, what, where, when, why and to whom. For example, "Manager added User to group Researchers. Manager is allowed to do this because Manager is the group owner of the group Researchers." Accounting in the EOSC-ENTRUST AAI focuses on access-related, event-level accountability, not on resource-usage accounting or billing. The purpose of accounting is to collect sufficient information to enable auditing of authentication, authorisation, and access-control decisions across the federation, while respecting privacy and proportionality principles.

6.3.1 Scope and data collection model

Accounting is closely linked to several components in the Blueprint. Therefore a centralized service, *Accounting Services*, where different components can send their accounting data is needed. Most of the accounting data collected is expected to come from the authorisation components of the AAI system, especially PEP and PDP as described in chapter 6.2 Authorisation and Access Control. Using an API-based data collection model enables both other components of the AAI services (e.g. Community Attribute Services, Proxy, etc.) and end services to send accounting information to *Accounting Services* regardless of their infrastructure or technology stacks.

6.3.2 Structured event model

To ensure interoperability across heterogeneous AAAI components and relying services, accounting data is collected using a minimal, technology-neutral structured event model. This model allows events originating from different systems to be expressed in a consistent format, enabling federation-wide correlation and analysis.

Collecting accounting data over a large federation can result in unmanageable amounts of data and may require TREs to expose operational details they are not willing or able to share. To avoid this, the central accounting/auditing service focuses on access-related events relevant for federation-wide traceability, rather than resource usage accounting such as compute/storage usage, billing, or quota consumption, which is out of scope for the AAAI system. Where TREs are willing and able to share access-related events centrally, the central accounting/auditing service may collect them. Otherwise, TREs need to maintain such events locally. This approach also mitigates the risk of creating a single, large collection of user data that would be an attractive target for attacks.

Core attributes of the structured event model include the acting subject, operation and outcome, timestamp, and source system, with optional attributes such as accessed object, policy context or reason, network and protocol information, IP address-derived geo-location, and an optional correlation identifier for cross-system tracing. Where this correlation identifier is not available, correlation may rely on existing subject identifiers and timestamps with reduced precision.

6.3.3 Event correlation

All logged data collected across the relevant components of the Blueprint should be correlated, so that events belonging to the same user access flow can be traced and associated during subsequent analysis. In most cases, authentication provides the initial context for this correlation, while subsequent authorisation decisions and resource access events extend the chain. Where events do not originate from an interactive authentication event, correlation should rely on available contextual identifiers and timestamps, in line with the structured event model.

6.3.4 Data minimisation and retention

Accounting data should not be stored indefinitely and should be subject to a retention policy. The length of accounting data storage should be unified across all services and components in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. Accounting data can be divided into categories based on age to lessen data storage and computation needs. The most recent data, called hot data, should be indexed and readily available. Intermediate data, called warm data, does not need to be indexed and readily available but should be accessible via the auditing UI. Old data, called cold data, can be encrypted and moved to separate storage to be stored until the retention period is passed and the data is deleted.

6.3.5 Auditing and access to accounting data

Auditing is the process of reviewing data collected in *Accounting*. Access to accounting data and by extension to *Auditing* should be restricted and controlled. A UI for reviewing accounting data should be offered. This UI should offer data analytics and reporting and may offer notification and alerts.

The main reasons to review accounting data are to ensure compliance or to investigate anomalous behaviour in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. The accounting data collected centrally should offer a view into what services or systems a user (or users originating from one home organisation for example) has accessed. Further data can then be requested from those services or systems based on correlation IDs.

More details on the structured event model, correlation mechanisms, retention considerations, and pilot implementations are described in the [EOSC-ENTRUST Accounting/Auditing Design Document \(EADD-001\)](#). This is a living document that collects the actual state, not just a frozen snapshot.

7. Revisions since AARC-BPA-2019-Final

The EOSC-ENTRUST AAI architecture introduces new components and adjustments to the original AARC BPA 2019 to better support the specific needs of the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. These revisions ensure enhanced security, compliance, and operational efficiency for managing user identities, authentication, and data handling within the system. The key revisions are as follows:

Account Creation:

A new Account Creation process has been added to the Community Attribute Service layer. This ensures that users have valid accounts before accessing member TREs in EOSC-ENTRUST. The process verifies whether a user has an existing account or whether a new one needs to be created with restricted access rights.

Identity Vetting:

The revised architecture introduces Identity Vetting for flexible integration with external identity vetting services, ensuring that identity verification can be handled through high-assurance electronic methods, such as eID or eKYC processes, that are essential for EOSC-ENTRUST's sensitive data processing requirements.

Attribute-Based Access Control:

The EOSC-ENTRUST AAI extends the AARC BPA 2019 authorisation model by introducing finer-grained attribute-based access control suitable for federated Trusted Research Environments. While the AARC BPA primarily addresses service-level authorisation,

EOOSC-ENTRUST AAAI enables access control decisions at the level of individual objects, such as datasets. In the ABAC model, access decisions are based on authorisation policies using attributes of the subject, object, operation, and environment. In addition to identity and group information, these attributes may include project context, agreements, training status, identity assurance, and other federation-relevant conditions.

Introduction of the Accounting Layer:

A significant revision to the original AARC BPA is the introduction of an Accounting Layer, which includes both the Accounting Service and the Auditing components. The Accounting Service collects and aggregates data from various components of the architecture, answering critical questions related to user actions and permissions. This centralised service enables better monitoring and ensures that all user actions are properly recorded for auditing purposes.

The Auditing component, closely tied to the Accounting Layer, enables the review and analysis of accounting data to ensure compliance with security policies and detect anomalous behaviour. This audit process is essential for maintaining transparency and accountability within the EOOSC-ENTRUST federation, particularly in environments with high-security requirements.

8. Conclusions

This document describes the year-two version of the AAAI for TREs Blueprint. Compared with the first version, it clarifies the role of the Blueprint as a federation-level reference architecture, refines the requirements based on driver feedback, and strengthens the security and interoperability baseline for implementations. The Blueprint will be evaluated in practice during the project's third year, as other work packages implement their demonstrators and the AAAI enhancements are integrated to support them. This hands-on evaluation, together with ongoing developments in the EOOSC Federation, AARC BPA, and OpenID Federation, will provide critical input for the final year-three version of the Blueprint.

9. Next Steps

The most important next step is the next and final version of this Blueprint. Under the project plan, it is scheduled for year 3, after gathering practical experience through the demonstrators the other work packages are planning.

There are currently many changes going on in the AAI space after years of relative quiet. The OpenID Federation specification is undergoing a voting period to be accepted as final

until mid-February⁸. The EOSC Federation is ramping up and has published a 2025 version of their Federation architecture [38], with a new version planned for late 2026. And finally, the AARC Blueprint Architecture, which forms the base of our architecture, is undergoing renewal. AARC has published an initial 2025 version of their architecture [39], but the final version is not yet complete.

Looking at these ongoing efforts, we have chosen to keep our architecture largely the same compared to last year's version [42]. We will eventually have to rebase our architecture on one, or more, of these building blocks. There have been comments from TRE operators that they expect to join the EOSC Federation through their national node. This, in turn, makes the EOSC Federation the most likely one for us to build on. EOSC Federation has been closely following the AARC BPA, but has also indicated that they may move to OpenID Federation after that specification is accepted as final. Taking all this into consideration, it is not a feasible approach for us to rebase our architecture at this time. Accordingly, we have decided to follow the developments in these three projects and then rebase the next version of our architecture based on those. We hope this will happen in time for the year-three version of our Blueprint.

This Blueprint provides the requirements and guidelines for the AAAI in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation but omits implementation details such as software choices or policy texts. These details will need to be settled as part of implementing the demonstrators on the AAAI side. As part of this, at least the following policies should be defined:

- Processing of personal data
- Privacy policy
- Acceptable use policy
- Data retention policy

There are a plethora of technical and implementation details that are beyond the scope of this Blueprint. AARC BPA solves this problem by having separate guidelines for technical and implementation details. We should adopt this same approach in EOSC-ENTRUST, making writing these guidelines an important next step. In this spirit we are preparing both the EOSC-ENTRUST Accounting/Auditing Design Document [40] and EOSC-ENTRUST Accounting/Auditing Service User Guide [41]. Neither document is part of this Blueprint nor a strict requirement for anyone implementing this Blueprint. Rather they offer guidance on how we are implementing the AAAI in effort to test our Blueprint and the EOSC-ENTRUST Federation.

In addition to software selection and other implementation details, the accounting service described here and in future guidelines should be evaluated against security guidelines. One such guideline is the EOSC Security Operational Baseline [23].

⁸ <https://openid.net/notice-of-vote-to-approve-proposed-openid-federation-1-0-final-specification/>

GA4GH has identified consortiums of organisations as a use case for authorisation decisions. While the AAAI already defines group memberships as a piece of information for authorisation decisions, consortium memberships for organisations are different and may need extra functionality. This is something that should be explored and clarified for future versions of this Blueprint.

GA4GH Passports and Visas are already in use at some TREs (e.g. CSC Sensitive Data services) and can be managed through software like REMS [18]. Including them in EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI must be considered. They are also going to be part of projects such as GDI [19] and were also mentioned in the preparation of Bigpicture [20]. The EOSC-ENTRUST AAAI must be built in collaboration with such projects and must be compatible with them. This is something that should be taken into account and ensured in the coming versions of this Blueprint.

Requirements R25 and R26 define identifiers for both projects and users respectively. The EOSC-ENTRUST overall architecture blueprint [26] places “Project registry” and “User registry” inside “Federation Services” but outside the AAAI. This is something that should be clarified in future versions of this Blueprint and the overall blueprint. The current plan is to implement AAAI services needed by EOSC-ENTRUST according to the architecture blueprint on top of Life Science AAI, which provides Life Science ID as globally unique, persistent, permanent and opaque identifier for users. It might be more beneficial to use this as the identifier for users in the EOSC-ENTRUST federation rather than building a new user registry.

Our approach aligns with and complements the objectives of sister EOSC projects SIESTA [43] and TITAN [44]. SIESTA focuses on enabling the secure re-use of sensitive research data by establishing trusted data sharing practices and services to ease the secure sharing through state-of-the-art anonymization techniques. TITAN has the overall objective of enriching the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) by developing a software platform solution for confidential collaboration and privacy-preserving data processing. Both projects could benefit from the AAAI for TREs architecture and implementation as they both need strong identity proofing and access control services. We plan to start closer work with the TITAN project for, e.g., to collect additional requirements that come from their work on the confidential collaboration and also to test our accounting/auditing enhancement against their plans for the auditing mechanisms for sensitive data and secure data sharing.

10. Impact

This document delivers the year-two version of the AAI for TREs Blueprint and takes further steps towards completing project objective 1.4: “Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals.” While the full impact of this Blueprint cannot be definitively assessed at this early stage, it is expected to set the standards, protocols, and practices that will underpin the integration of services and home organisations beyond the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. In the long term, this work will contribute to establishing a cohesive, secure, and interoperable infrastructure for TREs across Europe, laying the groundwork for enhanced collaboration and effective management of sensitive research data.

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